

DEPRESSION AMONG ADOLESCENT STUDENTS

Dr. Mandava Neelima

PRINCIPAL, Vikas college of Education Vissannapeta.

Paper Received On: 20 MAY 2025

Peer Reviewed On: 24 JUNE 2025

Published On: 01 JULY 2025

Abstract

In the present study the investigator adopted the descriptive survey method to find out the level, significant difference if any in the depression of adolescent students in terms of variables like gender, locality of college, mode of stay and private tuitions. The investigator used the simple random sampling technique. The sample consisted of 200 science group intermediate students of age between 16-17 years from 10 Junior college of rural and urban Vijayawada. Data was collected by face-to-face interview method. Tools used for data collection were the Beck depression inventory (BDI-II; A. T. Beck, R. A. Steer, & G. K. Brown, 1996) and personal information schedule. The study found that the depression of adolescent girls was higher than the adolescent boys. There is no significant difference between rural and urban adolescent students in their depression. There is no significant difference between day-scholar and hosteller adolescent students in their depression. There is no significant difference between private tuition going and non-going adolescent students in their depression.

Keywords: *Depression, Adolescent students Beck Depression Inventory*

1. INTRODUCTION

Globalization created tremendous employment opportunities in the field of IT and Science & Technology. The parents are interested to join their children in science and mathematics group ignoring their children's interest and capabilities in science and mathematics. Parental expectations and institutional expectations are causing stress among the intermediate students. For ages, it was a popular notion that children do not suffer from depression. Teenagers with depression were more often than not labelled as being just "difficult" or "moody". It is only recently that the world is awakening to the fact that up to 20% of world's children and adolescents suffer from disabling mental illnesses including depression. World Health Organization has included depression as one of the priority mental

Copyright © 2025, Scholarly Research Journal for Interdisciplinary Studies

disorders in childhood and adolescence. Adolescent depression not only interferes with emotional, social, and academic functioning but also is a proven risk factor for school absenteeism, educational under achievement, substance abuse and suicidal behaviour.

The American Psychological Association (APA) DSM-IV-TR(2000) states that the essential features of depressive episodes are either depressed mood (or possibly in children and adolescents an irritable mood) or loss of interest or pleasure in almost all activities and the associated symptoms of the disorder include weight change, sleep disturbance, psychomotor agitation or retardation, decreased energy, feelings of worthlessness or excessive or inappropriate guilt, difficulties in thinking or concentrating or suicidal ideations or attempts.

Depression disrupts a person's thinking processes, emotional reactions and day-by-day behaviours (Williams, 1984). Depression is an emotional state marked by great sadness and apprehension, feeling of worthlessness and guilt, withdrawal from others, loss of sleep, appetite and sexual desire, loss of interest and pleasure in usual activities. There are many factors that contribute to depression such as loneliness, lack of social support from family, peers, neighbours, financial strain, academic stress and negative influence of peers.

2. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE:

Depression in the normal individual include a state of sadness characterized by feeling of inadequacy, lowered activity, and hopelessness about the future, and in pathological cases, an extreme state of unresponsiveness to stimuli, together with self-depression, delusions of inadequacy and hopeless (Atkinson, Berne and Woodworth, 1988).

Beck and Beamesdefer suggest that characteristics of depression include hopelessness, sense of failure, self-dislike, social withdrawal, and somatic preoccupations.

Gupta, N. & Joshi studied the depression in relation to optimistic and pessimistic attitude among adolescent boys and girls. The finding of the present study revealed that boys as compared to girls were found to experience more depression. Further, the respondents having pessimistic attitude reported to feel more depression than the respondents who had reported optimistic attitude.

Gupta, Niti & Mathur studied the hopelessness among depressed university students; this study was designed to study hopelessness among low depressed and high depressed university female students. The findings reveal that higher depression higher is the hopelessness. Both the groups differ significantly on level of hopelessness.

Kumar Sanjay studied the prevalence of depression disorder among urban – rural population. The present study was aimed to investigate the prevalence of depression in urban – rural

population in Faridabad. Result shows a significant association between urban – rural population and male and females.

Suri, Aruna studied the depressive behaviour in relation to psychological determinants. This study was designed to investigate the main effects of depressive behaviour on intelligence and creativity and its interaction with locality and sex. Result showed the significant difference in the intellectual level of depressive and non depressive, urban and rural and male and female students.

From the above study it is clear that many studies have been done on depression with respect to various factors like academic achievement, health issues, behaviour and attitude. Present research work is aim to find out the level, significant difference if any in the depression of adolescent students in terms of variables like gender, locality of college, mode of stay and private tuitions.

3. OBJECTIVES:

1. To find out the relationship between adolescent boys and girls in their depression
2. To find out the relationship between rural and urban adolescent students in their depression
3. To find out the relationship between day-scholar and hosteller adolescent students in their depression
4. To find out the relationship between private tuition going and non-going adolescent students in their depression

4. HYPOTHESES

1. There is no significant difference between adolescent boys and girls in their depression.
2. There is no significant difference between rural and urban higher adolescent students in their depression.
3. There is no significant difference between day-scholar and hosteller adolescent students in their depression
4. There is no significant difference between private tuition going and non-going adolescent students in their depression.

5. DELIMITATIONS

1. The study was delimited to private college adolescent students (co-educated) of Vijayawada only.
2. The study was delimited to M.P.C/Bi.P.C group adolescent students only.
3. The study was delimited to intermediate first year students of age between 16-17 years only.

6. METHODOLOGY

Design of the Study: Descriptive survey method was used to find out the level, significant difference if any in the depression of adolescent students in terms of variables like gender, locality of college, mode of stay and private tuitions.

Sample of the Study: The investigator used the simple random sampling technique. The sample consisted of 200 (100 boys and 100 girls) students of age between 16-17 years studying M.P.C/ Bi.P.C groups from 10 Junior college of rural and urban Vijayawada.

Tools of the Study: The tools used in the study by the researcher were selected after a thorough analysis of literature on depression. The Tools used for data collection were the Beck Depression Inventory (BDI-II; A. T. Beck, R. A. Steer, & G. K. Brown, 1996), and personal information schedule.

1. Beck depression inventory (BDI-II) 2. Personal information schedule

Procedure: The inventories were distributed in the college. The students were given general instruction to complete the instrument in the order presented in Beck Depression Inventory (BDI-II) followed by personal information schedule the same questionnaires were given to the selected subjects immediately after the first year was over, the same inventories were given to the subjects.

Statistical Analysis: Beck Depression Inventory obtained from each subject was scored. Adolescent students were compared in terms of variables like gender, locality of college, mode of stay and private tuitions on the depression.

7. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. To find out the relationship between adolescent boys and girls in their depression.

Table-1

Difference between Adolescent boys and girl in their depression

S. No.	Gender	N	Mean	S.D	t-test	Level of significance
1	Boys	100	49.03	10.87	1.36	N S
2	Girls	100	50.67	9.33		

Non-significant At 5% level of significance

In table-1 the mean, standard deviation and t-value is presented. The mean score depression of Boys is 49.03 with S.D. of 10.87 and Girls has the mean and S.D. is 50.67 and 9.33. The t-ratio is calculated is 1.36 and Non-significant At 5% level of significance. It is inferred that there is no significant difference between adolescent boys and girls in their depression.

2. To find out the relationship between rural and urban Adolescent students in their depression

Table-2

Difference between rural and urban Adolescent students in their depression

S. No.	Locality of college	N	Mean	S.D	t-test	Level of significance
1	Rural	100	50.15	10.49	0.263	N S
2	Urban	100	49.84	9.51		

Non-significant At 5% level of significance

In table-2 the mean, standard deviation and t-value is presented. The mean score depression of rural adolescent students is 50.15 with S.D. of 10.49 and urban adolescent students has the mean and S.D. is 49.84 and 9.51. The t-ratio is calculated is 1.36 and Non-significant At 5% level of significance. It is inferred that there is no significant difference between rural and urban adolescent students in their depression.

3. To find out the relationship between day-scholar and hosteller Adolescent students in their depression

Table-3

Difference between day-scholar and hosteller Adolescent students in their depression

S. No.	Mode of Stay	N	Mean	S.D	t-test	Level of significance
1	Day-scholars	100	48.99	10.458	1.43	N S
2	Hostellers	100	50.70	9.636		

Non-significant At 5% level of significance

In table-3 the mean, standard deviation and t-value is presented. The mean score depression of day-scholar adolescent students is 48.99 with S.D. of 10.458 and hostel adolescent students has the mean and S.D. is 50.70 and 9.636. The t-ratio is calculated is 1.43 and Non-significant At 5% level of significance. It is inferred that there is no significant difference between day-scholar and hosteller adolescent students in their depression.

4. To find out the relationship between private tuition going and non-going Adolescent students in their depression.

Table-4

Difference between private tuition going and non-going Adolescent students in their depression

S. No.	Private tuitions	N	Mean	S.D	t-test	Level of significance
1	Going	100	49.55	9.66	1.23	N S
2	Non-Going	100	51.28	10.87		

Non-significant At 5% level of significance

In table the mean, standard deviation and t-value is presented. The mean score depression of Private tuitions Going Day-scholar adolescent students is 49.55 with S.D. of 9.66 and Private

tutions Non-Going adolescent students has the mean and S.D. is 51.28 and 10.87. The t-ratio is calculated is 1.23 and Non-significant At 5% level of significance. It is inferred that there is no significant difference between private tuition going and non-going adolescent students in their depression.

8. EDUCATIONAL IMPLICATIONS

1. Teachers and parents are to be sensitive to the adolescent's, to recognize their problems and deal with them.
2. Teachers are to be flexible with timelines and work load of the students.
3. Teachers are not to insult and not to give corporal punishment and not to encourage cut throat competitions.
4. The institution has to help the students by arranging necessary programmes on life coping skills, time management, aversion techniques, relaxation techniques and awareness programmes on health issues especially at intermediate level.

9. CONCLUSION

The investigator found that the depression of adolescent girls was higher than the adolescent boys. There is no significant difference between rural and urban adolescent students in their depression. There is no significant difference between day-scholar and hosteller adolescent in their depression. There is no significant difference between private tuition going and non-going adolescent students in their depression.

REFERENCES

- American Psychological Association (APA) DSM-IV-TR (2000)
- Atkinson, J., Berne, E., & Woodworth, R.S. (1988)
- Beck, A.T. (1967). *Depression: Clinical, experimental and theoretical aspects*, Newyork: Hoeber.
- Beck, A. T., & Beamesderfer, A. (1974), *Assessment of depression: Depression Inventory*. In P.Pichot (Ed.), *Psychological measurements in Psychopathology: Modern problems in pharma psychiatry*. Basel: S.Karger. (PP.151-169).
- Gupta, Niti & Mathur, Meena "Hopelessness Among Depressed University Students", *Indian Journal of Psychometric & Educations*, Vol. 36 (2), 2005, PP- 114-119.
- Kumar, Sanjay "Prevalence of Depression disorder among urban – rural population" *Indian Journal of Psychometric & Education*, 2003, PP-125-130.
- Suri, Aruna, "Depressive Behavior in relation to Psychological Determinants", *Indian journal of Psychometric and education* , Vol-32, 2001, PP- 97– 99.
- Saxena's & Gyanani , T.C. "Frustrations Reaction Patterns as a Function of Gender, Cognitive Style and Conformity at Different Age Level's" ,*Behavioral Scientist*, vol. 5 (1), 2004 PP -59-64 .
- Williams, C. A. (1984). *Factor analysis of Maslach Burnout Inventory data*. Unpublished raw data. In C. Kanta (2004), *A study of psychological correlates of depression among nurses*. Unpublished Ph.D. thesis, Panjab University, Chandigarh.
- World Health Organization *Caring for children and adolescents with mental disorders Geneva* (2003)
- Copyright © 2025, Scholarly Research Journal for Interdisciplinary Studies